

STRUCTURAL DYNAMICS AND INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF ELASTOMER NANO-COMPOSITES

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SUMMMARY

The combined effect of filler networking and reduced chain mobility close to the filler interface on the dynamic-mechanical properties of elastomers is analyzed based on investigations of the relaxation dynamics of solution styrene butadiene rubber filled with different loadings of silica. Dynamic-mechanical and dielectric spectra are studied in a wide frequency and temperature range. For the creation of dynamic-mechanical master curves frequency dependent measurements at different temperatures are applied to cover a larger frequency range. It is demonstrated that the time-temperature-superposition (TTS)-principle is not fulfilled for filled elastomers and the introduction of vertical shift factors is necessary to obtain viscoelastic master curves. The changes in the dynamic-mechanical properties by the incorporation of fillers and the failure of the TTS-principle in the low frequency (high temperature) regime are shown to be related to the superimposed dynamics of the filler network. It is governed by the viscoelastic response of glassy-like polymer bridges between adjacent filler particles, which differs from that of the polymer matrix. The reduced chain mobility close to the filler interface becomes apparent by a broadening of the glass transition on the high temperature side.

Keywords: dynamic-mechanical analysis, dielectric spectroscopy, filler reinforcement, molecular dynamics, time-temperature superposition

INTRODUCTION

The field of application of elastomers is determined by their frequency dependent dynamic-mechanical properties, which are connected with characteristic relaxation and energy dissipation mechanisms depending on frequency, temperature and amplitude. They are strongly affected by the bonding of the polymer chains to the filler interface, the polymer-filler interphase dynamics and the specific filler network effects. For a better understanding and for getting a deeper insight into structure and dynamics of elastomer nano-composites, it is important to investigate the relations between filler network morphology, interphase dynamics and bulk viscoelastic properties on a broad frequency scale [1-3].

The viscoelastic properties are important entities for several rubber technological applications. In particular, it has been demonstrated how viscoelastic master curves can be used for modeling hysteresis and adhesion friction of elastomers on rough, self-affine surfaces and how other contact parameters as e.g. the real area of contact can be evaluated [4,5]. In addition, it has been shown how viscoelasticity in the high frequency

regime impacts the fracture mechanical properties as the crack growth rate of elastomers under cyclic loading [6].

In the present approach the combined effect of filler networking and reduced chain mobility close to the filler interface on the dynamic-mechanical properties of elastomers is analyzed based on investigations of the relaxation dynamics of solution styrene butadiene rubber filled with different loadings of nano-structured fillers. Dynamic-mechanical and dielectric spectra are studied in a wide frequency and temperature range. For the creation of dynamic-mechanical master curves frequency dependent measurements at different temperatures are applied to cover a larger frequency range. It will be demonstrated that the time-temperature-superposition (TTS)-principle is not fulfilled for filled elastomers due to the superimposed dynamics of the filler network, which is dominated by the viscoelastic response of glassy-like polymer bridges between adjacent filler particles. The reduced chain mobility close to the filler interface will be discussed and related to the observed broadening of the glass transition on the low frequency side, which becomes also visible in the relaxation time spectra.

EXPERIMENTAL

The samples have been prepared with two different styrol-butadiene rubbers (VSL 5025-0, 25% styrol content, 50% vinyl content and VSL 2525-0, 25% styrol content, 25% vinyl content (both Lanxess, Germany), which were filled with different loadings of silica (Ultrasil GR 7000, Evonik Degussa GmbH). The content of silane TESPT (Bis-(triethoxysilylpropyl)tetrasulfane) was varied between 1.7 and 6.7 phr in dependence of the filler content due to the changing amount of reactive silanole groups with increasing filler content. 3 phr zinc oxide, 1 phr stearic acid, 2 phr N-isopropyl-N'-phenyl-p-phenyldiamine (IPPD), 2,5 phr n-cyclohexyl-2-benzothiazole-sulfenamide (CBS) and 1,7 phr soluble sulfur were used as vulcanisation system.

The composites were prepared in an internal mixer rotating at 50 rpm in a multi-step-mixing procedure. At first the rubber and the silica were mixed in the internal mixer at 140°C. The silane was added for in-situ-silanisation at 150°C and the silanisation reaction was performed during 10 min. In second step after 24 hours the masterbatch was again mixed in the internal mixer at 130 °C for 8 min to ensure the silanization reaction is completed. In a third step the rest of anti aging additives and curatives was added at 40°C on the two-roll mill. The curing study was carried out with the help of a rheometer (Monsanto ME 2000) at 160°C. The samples were cured under pressure at 160°C to 2 mm plates in dependence of the determined t_{90} vulcanization time.

Dielectric investigations have been carried out in a wide temperature range (-100 °C to +100 °C) and at frequencies from 0.1 Hz to 10 MHz using a broadband dielectric spectrometer BDS 40 (Novocontrol GmbH, Germany). The temperature was varied in five-degree steps using the temperature control system Novocool. The temperature uncertainty amounts to ± 0.5 °C. The measured geometry was a disc shaped plate capacitor with a diameter of 40 mm. The sample with a thickness of 2 mm was placed between two gold-plated electrodes. To provide an excellent contact between sample and electrodes thin gold layers have been sputtered onto the flat surface of the sample plate. A force-limiting spring was used to ensure that always the same clamping force was exerted onto the test-capacitor keeping thickness and electrical contact as comparable as possible between different samples. The dielectric permittivity and the dielectric loss have been recorded for each sample in dependence of temperature and frequency.

The dynamic-mechanical measurements were performed in the torsion-rectangular mode with strip specimen of 2 mm thickness and 30 mm length with an ARES rheometer (Rheometric). The dynamic moduli were measured over a wide temperature range (-80 °C to +80 °C) at a frequency of 1 Hz and 0.5% strain amplitude for temperature dependent measurements. For creating dynamic-mechanical master curves frequency dependent measurements have been performed at different temperatures between +60°C and -60°C in five degree steps varying the frequency between 0,01 Hz and 16 Hz. The strain amplitude was kept constant at 0.5 %.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of horizontal shifting factors

For the construction of viscoelastic master curves of filler reinforced rubbers it is necessary to evaluate the horizontal shifting factors related to the time-temperature superposition of the rubber matrix. This can be done by referring to the horizontal shifting behaviour of the unfilled samples or, in the case of silica filled samples, by direct measurements of the dielectric loss peak during the glass transition on a broad frequency and temperature scale [4-6].

Fig. 1: Dielectric loss permittivity of the S-SBR sample VSL 5025-0 filled with 60 phr silica (a) and the corresponding activation diagram (b). Fitting lines with adapted parameters are indicated.

Fig. 1 shows two dielectric loss peaks of the S-SBR sample VSL 5025-0 filled with 60 phr silica (a) and the corresponding activation diagram (b). The low temperature peak can be assigned to fluctuations of a confined layer of water molecules at the silica surface and is typically described by an Arrhenius behaviour with activation energy of about 0.6 eV, corresponding to roughly three hydrogen bonds per water molecules similar as in frozen water [7]. The observed high temperature peak is related to the glass transition of the matrix and has been fitted by the well known Vogel-Fulcher equation:

$$f = f_{\infty} \cdot \exp\left\{-\frac{E_A}{R(T - T_{VF})}\right\} \quad (1)$$

The activation energy $E_A \approx 0.15$ eV obtained from the Vogel-Fulcher fit is much lower than that for confined hydration water and can be assigned to van der Waals interaction between the polymer chains. The Vogel-Fulcher temperature $T_{VF} \approx -75$ °C indicates the critical state where the free volume becomes zero. It is found to be about 65 °C below the glass transition temperature $T_g \approx -10$ °C of the S-SBR samples, measured e.g. by DSC, where cooperative chain movements are frozen.

Fig. 2 shows the temperature dependent horizontal shifting factors $a_T \equiv \tau(T)/\tau(T_{ref})$ of the unfilled and silica filled S-SBR samples VSL 5025-0 for the reference temperature $T_{ref} = 20$ °C. They are obtained from Vogel-Fulcher fits of dielectric loss data with the characteristic relaxation time taken as $\tau = 1/f(\epsilon''_{max})$. It is found that the horizontal shift factors, describing the time-temperature superposition of the matrix, are not influenced by the presence of the filler, i.e. the location of the loss peak related to the glass transition is the same for filled and unfilled samples. Furthermore, the horizontal shift factors obtained from dynamic-mechanical investigations of the unfilled samples are the same as those obtained from dielectric data. This is in agreement with previous investigations showing that this procedure is successful since the underlying cooperative processes causing the glass transition process are identical in both investigation measurement methods [4]. This indicates that the dielectric loss peak refers to cooperative movements of the rubber chain backbone and not e.g. that of side groups. Accordingly, the dielectric data can be used for the evaluation of horizontal shift factors and the construction of viscoelastic master curves also for the filled samples.

Fig. 2: Horizontal shift factors at reference temperature $T_{ref} = 20$ °C for the unfilled and silica filled S-SBR samples VSL 5025-0 from dielectric data.

Dynamic-mechanical measurements have been performed by varying the frequency at various constant temperatures. By applying the time-temperature superposition principle for the unfilled polymer the different branches have been shifted horizontally to obtain viscoelastic master curves. The horizontal shift factors obtained in this way for the unfilled S-SBR sample VSL 2525-0 are plotted as a function of temperature in Fig. 3.

As reference temperature again $T_{ref} = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is chosen. In addition, the horizontal shift factors for the unfilled and filled samples have been determined using dielectric relaxation spectroscopy by extracting the local maxima of the dielectric loss of the glass transition process. The resulting shift factors for the unfilled sample and the samples filled with 40 phr and 80 phr of Silica are as well included in Fig. 3. Obviously, the location of the glass transition of the matrix, indicated by the loss maxima, is not affected by the presence of filler. Accordingly, all samples can be described by a single set of horizontal shift factors. The solid line in Fig. 3 demonstrates that all samples can be fitted by the well known Williams-Landel-Ferry (WLF) equation [8]:

$$\log(a_T) = \frac{-C_1 \cdot (T - T_{ref})}{C_2 + (T - T_{ref})}, \text{ for } T_g < T < T_g + 100^\circ\text{C} \quad (2)$$

The resulting WLF-constants are found as $C_1 = 5,15$ and $C_2 = 126,57$. We point out that the identical set of horizontal shift factors for the unfilled and filled samples does not mean that the whole dynamics of the polymer matrix remains unchanged, since a broadening of the glass transition loss maximum is generally observed with increasing filler loading. Note that the two constants C_1 and C_2 are related to the parameters of the Vogel-Fulcher Equ. (1) and the reference temperature T_{ref} as $C_1 = E_A/R(T_{ref} - T_{VF})$ and $C_2 = T_{ref} - T_{VF}$, with R being the gas constant. If the reference temperature is taken as the glass transition temperature, the two constants for many diene rubbers have almost universal values $C_1 = 17.4$ and $C_2 = 51.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [8].

Fig. 3: Horizontal shift factors at reference temperature $T_{ref} = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for unfilled and silica filled S-SBR samples VSL 2525-0 determined by dynamic-mechanical data (open symbol) and dielectric spectroscopy (filled symbols), as indicated; The solid line represents a fit according to the WLF-Equ. (2).

Viscoelastic master curves of filled elastomers

Fig. 4 shows the constructed master curves for the unfilled and filled S-SBR samples VSL 2525-0 by applying the single set of horizontal shifting factors obtained in Fig. 3 by the adaptation to Equ. (2). It demonstrates explicitly that the horizontal shifting leads to a well matching master curve for the unfilled samples. For the filled samples with

increasing filler content a increasing discontinuity of the single branches at low frequencies is observed. Obviously in these cases the time-temperature superposition is not fulfilled.

Fig. 4: Master curves of the storage modulus G' of an unfilled S-SBR sample VSL 2525-0 and the same samples filled with 60 and 80 phr of silica created with horizontal shift factors from the unfilled sample (a); Arrhenius dependence of the vertical shift factors for the filled samples (b).

The data in Fig. 4 show that master curves for unfilled polymer networks or melts can be constructed on a broad frequency scale by applying the time-temperature superposition principle. This is based on the fact that all characteristic relaxation times, as e.g. Rouse relaxation- or tube reptation time, can be traced back to the temperature dependent diffusion time of the monomer units on a molecular length scale. For polymer blends with different glass transition temperatures or filled elastomers with interpenetrating networks this is no longer the case, since the mechanical response results from additive network contributions with different dynamics. This kind of superposition of interpenetrating networks with different relaxation behaviour implies that one network component is governing the mechanical response of the whole system in a certain temperatures or frequency regime and the other component in another. In the case of filler reinforced elastomers the low temperature (high frequency) mechanical response mainly results from the glassy polymer matrix, while the high temperature (low frequency) response is dominated by the filler network, provided the filler network is significantly stiffer than the polymer matrix. Accordingly, at low frequencies the Arrhenius like thermal activation of the filler network, resulting from the immobilized polymer bridges between adjacent filler particles, can not be compensated by the WLF-like horizontal shifting factors of the polymer matrix and discontinuous branches are found for the filled samples in Fig. 4 (a). Fair overlapping of the branches can only be obtained at high frequencies beyond the glass transition of the matrix, which then dominates the mechanical response of the system.

Since it was demonstrated that the horizontal shift factors are independent of the filler content it was necessary to use vertical shift factors to compensate the mismatches. An Arrhenius-plot of the vertical shift factors is shown in Fig. 4 (b). For all filled samples a fair linear behaviour of the vertical shift factors is found in the temperature range above

the glass transition of the matrix indicating a thermally activated process causes the deviation in the master curves. The slope can be interpreted as an apparent activation energy of the filler network, resulting from glassy-like polymer bridges between adjacent filler particles which form the filler-filler bonds [4-6]. The so obtained activation energies are summarized in Table 1. They increase almost linearly with increasing filler loading, indicating that there is a change of the dynamics of the glassy bridges resulting either from an decreasing gap size of filler-filler bonds or from an increasing influence of overlapping regions of adjacent filler particles with rising filler concentration. This correlates with the experimental observation that the glass transition temperature of ultra-thin films between attractive walls decreases strongly with film thickness if the thickness falls below 20 nm [9-11]. The gap size between adjacent filler particles of the filler network typically lies in the range of a few nm [2,3], implying strong effects of the gap spacing on mechanical properties of filler-filler bonds, e.g. stiffness, strength or activation energy.

Table 1: Comparison of the activation energies determined by temperature dependent measurements of G' (Fig. 6) and vertical shifting to obtain G' master-curves for the silica filled S-SBR sample VSL 2525-0 depicted in Fig. 4 (b).

	Temperature sweeps	Vertical shifting
0 phr	0.03 ± 0.02 kJ/mol	0 kJ/mol
20 phr	0.93 ± 0.10 kJ/mol	0.66 ± 0.12 kJ/mol
40 phr	3.26 ± 0.06 kJ/mol	2.62 ± 0.36 kJ/mol
60 phr	6.66 ± 0.18 kJ/mol	5.15 ± 0.2 kJ/mol
80 phr	11.22 ± 0.20 kJ/mol	8.67 ± 0.2 kJ/mol

Fig. 5: Master curves of the storage modulus G' of the unfilled and silica filled S-SBR samples VSL 2525-0 after application of horizontal and vertical shifting (a); Relaxation time spectra of the investigated samples (b).

The dynamic-mechanical master curves after applying vertical shifting are shown in Fig. 5 (a). An increasing frequency dependence of the master curves at low frequencies

is observable with increasing filler loading. Since the filler network is dominating the mechanical response in the low frequency regime we can conclude that this behaviour is due to an increasing stiffness of the filler network. Accordingly, the observed frequency dependence is due to the frequency response of the glassy-like polymer bridges between adjacent filler particles forming the filler-filler bonds. Nevertheless, with rising frequency just below the glass transition frequency an additional effect results from the growing polymer shells with slowed-down dynamics around the filler particles. This effect becomes more pronounced for large loadings, since the amount of polymer matrix forming a gradient of reduced mobility in the vicinity of the filler surface is increasing with filler concentration. This effects can be related to the observed broadening of the glass transition regime on the low frequency side with increasing filler loading.

The role of filler-filler bonds, on the one side, and the slowed-down dynamics close to filler particles, on the other side, in dynamic-mechanical properties can be analyzed on different time scales by referring to the relaxation time spectra depicted in Fig. 5 (b). They have been calculated from the master curves of G' according to the iterative approximation method of Ferry and Williams [8,12]:

$$H(\tau) = AG' d \log G' / d \log \omega \Big|_{1/\omega=\tau} \text{ for } m < 1 \text{ with } A = (2-m) / \left(2\Gamma\left(2-\frac{m}{2}\right)\Gamma\left(1+\frac{m}{2}\right) \right) \quad (3)$$

Here m is the local slope of H at $\tau=1/\omega$, which must be smaller than one, and Γ is the gamma function. Fig. 5 (b) demonstrates that the presence of fillers modifies the behavior of the relaxation time spectrum during the glass transition, i.e. a less pronounced drop of relaxation time contributions is found. On time scales 10^{-8} to 10^{-3} s a power law behaviour is more or less realized and the scaling exponent increases from about -0.6 to -0.4 with increasing filler loading. This is directly related to the observed broadening of the glass transition in Figs. 5 (a) and 6 resulting from the slowed-down dynamics close to filler particles. Nevertheless, a full theoretical understanding of the modified power law exponent due to confined polymer shells around filler particles is outstanding so far. Furthermore, one observes a considerable contribution of relaxation times larger than 10^{-3} s which also increases with filler loading. This relaxation at longer time scales is attributed to the filler network.

The impact of the filler network with thermally activated filler-filler bonds can also be observed for the temperature dependent viscoelastic data. An Arrhenius-plot of the storage modulus G' measured at 1 Hz is shown in Fig. 6 for all VSL 2525-0 samples. As indicated by the inserted regression lines one observes a thermal activation of G' in the high temperature range, which becomes more pronounced with increasing filler content. This effect is typical for elastomers filled with highly reinforcing fillers [13,14]. In a plot of $\log G'$ as a function of the inverse temperature the differences in this behaviour with increasing filler content can be quantified calculating the value for the slope n in a defined temperature range following an Arrhenius like behaviour. The slope $n = -E_A/R$, where R is the gas constant, corresponds to an activation energy which is physically related to the thermal activation of the filler-filler bonds. In analogy to the vertical shifting factors depicted in Fig. 4 (b), this slope is increasing with increasing filler content, resulting in an increasing activation energy of the glassy bridges. But as slightly visible in Fig. 6 the linear function dominates the behaviour of $\log G'$ in dependence of the inverse temperature but do not describe the behaviour of G' completely. An underlying potential function, introduced in [15-17] describes the change of the elastic modulus due to the increase of the thickness of a glassy shell around the filler particles with decreasing temperature. Both effects are difficult to

separate, though the most significant contribution of the growing shells results close to the glass transition temperature T_g leading to the observed broadening of the glass transition on the high temperature side. For temperatures higher than about $T_g + 30$ °C the Arrhenius-fits in Fig. 6 represents a reasonable description of the experimental data, confirming the conclusion from the frequency dependent data (Fig. 5) that the filler network is dominating the behaviour of G' in this regime. The systematic deviations from the Arrhenius behaviour at higher temperatures can be explained by an increase of the cross-section of the glassy-like polymer bridges (filler-filler bonds) with decreasing temperature as indicated in the inset of Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Arrhenius plot of the temperature dependent measurements of the storage modulus of the silica filled S-SBR samples VSL 2525-0; Inset: Schematic view of modified polymer dynamics in the vicinity of filler particles.

A comparison of the activation energies resulting from vertical shifting and temperature dependent measurements is shown in Tab. 1, giving slightly higher values for the activation energies obtained by temperature dependent measurements. Furthermore, with increasing filler content the difference between the activation energies is increasing. This can be related to the stronger incline of the frequency dependent modulus with increasing filler content observed in Fig. 5, indicating a more pronounced stiffening of filler-filler bonds. Accordingly, the horizontal shifting compensates larger parts of the thermal activation of filler-filler bonds as derived from the temperature dependent measurements in Fig. 6. We finally point out that the detected characteristic load dependence, i.e. the increase of the activation energy and the stronger frequency response of glassy-like polymer bridges indicate that the bond length or gap distance decreases slightly with increasing filler concentration leading to filler-filler bonds with different mechanical properties and relaxation dynamics.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that the viscoelastic response of the elastic modulus G' of filler reinforced elastomers at high temperatures (low frequencies) is due to a combination of two effects: On the one hand side, the slowing down of the dynamics of the polymer matrix close to the filler surface leads to a broadening of the glass transition on the high temperature (low frequency) side. This may be considered by an underlying potential

function, which describes the thickness of a glassy layer around filler particles [15-17]. On the other hand side, due to its higher stiffness compared to the polymer matrix, the filler network governs the small strain dynamic-mechanical properties of the composites in the high temperatures (low frequency) regime. Accordingly, the viscoelastic response is due to glassy-like polymer bridges between adjacent filler particles. In a plot of $\log G'$ against the inverse temperature an Arrhenius like behaviour is obtained, which describes the thermal activation of filler-filler bonds (Fig. 6).

Since the viscoelastic response of the filler network, i.e. glassy-like polymer bridges, differs from that of the polymer matrix, the time-temperature superposition principle is not fulfilled. This implies a failure of the master procedure making the introduction of vertical shift factors necessary (Fig. 4). The vertical shift factors show an Arrhenius like behaviour, which can again be related to the activation energy of glassy-like polymer bridges. At low frequencies, the resulting master curves of the storage modulus reflect the increasing stiffness of filler-filler bonds with rising frequency. At intermediate frequencies just below the glass transition, an additional stiffening of the composite results due to an increasing thickness of the glassy polymer layers around filler particles and the increasing influence of overlapping region of adjacent filler particles (Fig. 5).

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